

EM-TECH

D7.3 – Report on communication and exploitation activities, sustainability concept

EM-TECH - Innovative e-motor technologies covering e-axles and e-corners vehicle architectures for high-efficient and sustainable e-mobility

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long Version
AFM	Axial Flux Motor
BEPA	Batteries European Partnership Association
BMC	Business Model Canvas
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected & Automated Mobility
CRM	Critical Raw Materials
EGVIAfor2Zero	European Green Vehicles Initiative Association for the 2Zero partnership

EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
ERTRAC	European Road Transport Research Advisory Council
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
EV	Electric Vehicle
GA	Grant Agreement
HiL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
IWM	In-wheel Motor
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PO	Project Outcome
RTR	Road Transport Research
R&D&I	Research & Development & Innovation
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SoC	System on Chip
TRA	Transport Research Arena
VPC	Value Proposition Canvas
XiL	X-in-the-Loop

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 Overview of project

EM-TECH brings together 10 participants from industry and academia to develop novel solutions to push the boundaries of electric machine technology for automotive traction, through: i) innovative direct and active cooling designs; ii) virtual sensing functionalities; iii) enhanced machine control; iv) electric gearing; v) digital twin based optimization for a systematic consideration of Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) aspects; and vi) adoption of recycled permanent magnets (PMs) and circularity solutions. These innovations will be implemented in new series of in-wheel motors (IWMs) and on-board axial flux machines (AFMs), addressing both passenger car and van applications.

1.2 Deliverable Objective and Results

This deliverable D7.3 aims to provide an overview of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities conducted as well as the sustainability concept, and outlines the results from the frameworks and tools applied.

The outlined communication activity highlights are (1) the project video, (2) the project partner videos, and (3) the final webinar series. Concerning dissemination activity (1) the TRA conference, (2) the RTR conference, (3) the SAE WCX™, and (4) the successful publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals have been highlighted. In terms of exploitation, EM-TECH project partners have been surveyed on their exploitation pathways and supported by the joint application of the Value Proposition Canvas (VPC) and Business Model Canvas (BMC), increasing the likelihood of a three-layered fit between the partners' value proposition and the identified customer segments as well as improving the understanding of the own business(es). In-depth assessments of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities are not part of this deliverable D7.3 but will be included in EM-TECH's final reporting.

The sustainability concept section contains (1) information on the nine generated one pagers on EM-TECH's project outcomes, (2) the results gained from a macro-environment analysis of the EM-TECH project by utilizing PESTEL and Porter's Five Forces, and (3) an outlook on the market situation, roadmaps, and trends of the automotive ecosystem provided by a joint publication in press.

2 Introduction

This deliverable reports on the topics of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities conducted throughout the entire three years of project duration and the project's sustainability concept.

Over the project lifetime, communication and dissemination activities have been performed to increase the visibility of EM-TECH among a set of stakeholders. The exploitation dimension has focused on identifying pathways for uptake and further development of EM-TECH's project outcomes (POs), which has been supported by utilizing the Value Proposition Canvas (VPC) and Business Model Canvas (BMC) for each project partner. The sustainability concept discusses mechanisms to maximize the project's impact beyond project termination, ensuring long-term relevance of EM-TECH's technological advancements. To retrieve a better understanding of the project partners macro-environment in the context of the EM-TECH project, the PESTEL analysis and Porter's Five Forces have been applied and the results included in this deliverable.

Building upon the deliverable D7.2, this deliverable D7.3 aims to provide an overview of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities conducted as well as the sustainability concept, and outlines the results from the frameworks and tools applied.

3 Project communication

The EM-TECH project communication includes every action taken to inform, promote, and communicate activities in the context of EM-TECH and its project results throughout the entire project duration. The project's communication aims to (1) ensure clear, coherent, and timely communication about EM-TECH's objectives, activities, progress, and overall value to society, (2) raise broad awareness about all aspects of EM-TECH for the public at large, (3) increase the engagement with potential stakeholders, including also those beyond the immediate R&D community, (4) showcase EU-funded R&D actions and areas of research, and (5) provide information about successful collaboration between project partners across Europe.

All communication activities in the EM-TECH project focus on:

- Explaining why the project is relevant, which challenges it addresses, and how it contributes to European and global priorities,
- Making the project and its activities visible to relevant target audiences through accessible and engaging formats,
- Supporting transparency and accountability by regularly informing the public about project progress, milestones, and key developments, and
- Building interest and trust around the project, thereby facilitating subsequent dissemination and exploitation of results.

Communication activities have been implemented from the early stages of the EM-TECH project and continued throughout its duration. They are coordinated across partners and aligned with the

communication channels described in the next chapter and visual identity to ensure consistent messaging. The level of technical detail has been adapted to different target groups, with a strong emphasis on clarity, inclusiveness, and accessibility. Moreover, the upcoming subsections include highlights of the project communication, and an overview of the project communication activities performed in EM-TECH in general.

3.1 Communication channels

The EM-TECH project utilizes a set of different communication channels. The three most important channels are shortly described in the following subsections.

3.1.1 Project website

The project website served as the central communication hub throughout the project duration. It provided up-to-date and publicly accessible information on project objectives, activities, results, and events. The landing page of EM-TECH's project website can be reached via <https://emtechproject.eu> and is illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Landing page of EM-TECH's website

Key functions of the project website include:

- presenting the EM-TECH project, its objectives and impact as well as the project consortium and the international advisory board,
- offering download access to project identity material (in the contact section) as well as public deliverables and research papers (in the results section),
- hosting project news, event announcements and recaps,
- serving as a research platform for all project results like interviews, deliverables, scientific publications, posters, presentations, newsletters, reports, etc., and
- main communication channel for promoting (announcement and registration) the EM-TECH final webinar series and presenting the respective recordings.

The EM-TECH project website has been continuously updated to reflect the project’s progress and to ensure transparency and visibility for both scientific and industrial audiences.

Throughout the years 2023 until 2025, the EM-TECH website attracted significant numbers of (unique) visitors: on average 329 per year in 2023, 746 in 2024, and 1.248 in 2025.

3.1.2 EM-TECH’s LinkedIn Channel

The project’s LinkedIn channel via <https://www.linkedin.com/company/em-tech-project> acted as the primary social media platform for engaging with professional audiences and amplifying project visibility across the European research & development & innovation (R&D&I) ecosystem.

Through regular posts, the channel communicated:

- Milestones and achievements,
- Partner spotlights and consortium activities,
- Announcements and recaps of general assemblies and internal meetings,
- Participation in conferences, workshops, and cluster events,
- Dissemination of publications, deliverables, and interviews,
- Promotion of the Final Webinar Series, and
- Relevant external news and synergies with other EU-funded R&D initiatives.

LinkedIn proved to be an effective tool to reach out for researchers, stakeholders from academic and industry, policymakers, and clusters in EM-TECH’s field of research. Engagement metrics (followers, impressions, and total page views) show a steady increase over the project lifetime and are outlined in Table 1 in detail.

Table 1: EM-TECH's LinkedIn metrics

Year	Impressions	Total page views	Followers
2023	14.724	1.111	203
2024	16.792	1.418	137
2025	24.902	676	228

Over the entire project duration 56.418 impressions have been generated, 3205 page views achieved, and 568 followers attracted.

3.1.3 E-VOLVE Cluster Membership

The EM-TECH project is an active member of the E-VOLVE Cluster, which significantly enhanced the project’s outreach and dissemination through their established communication ecosystem in the field of electric mobility. As part of the membership, EM-TECH benefited from the cluster’s multi-channel communication, including:

Cluster Website: Project updates, event participation, and news items were published on the cluster website, expanding the project’s visibility towards a broader community of EU-funded projects, industrial partners, research institutions, policymakers, and other stakeholders.

Cluster LinkedIn Channel: Regular resharing of EM-TECH's posts and dedicated cluster highlights further increased the outreach. The cluster audience brought additional exposure to stakeholders beyond EM-TECH's direct professional network.

Cluster Twitter Account: The cluster's Twitter/X account provided short, timely updates on project developments, especially during events, conferences, and joint initiatives.

Cluster Newsletter: The cluster's periodic newsletter included several mentions of the project, featuring (1) progress updates, (2) announcements of events and webinars, and (3) highlights of key results and publications.

This ensured that EM-TECH was regularly promoted to the E-VOLVE cluster's subscriber base, including policymakers, national contact points, industry representatives, and academic networks. In addition, the newsletter issues have been published on Zenodo as open-access resources to ensure wider community outreach.

3.2 Highlights

A couple of communication activities have been selected to be included in this highlights section, pointing out their objectives, target audiences, timing, and contribution to the overall EM-TECH project impact.

3.2.1 Project video

A project video has been produced and released for mid-term reporting as a key communication activity to mark entry of the final year of the EM-TECH project. Developed through the collaborative involvement of all project partners, the project video presented EM-TECH's overall vision, objectives, and expected societal relevance in an accessible and engaging format.

The project video aimed to revitalize communication efforts for the final project phase, creating renewed momentum and visibility while reinforcing a shared sense of ownership among partners. By using clear, non-technical language and visual storytelling, the video successfully conveyed the project's added value and progress to a broad, non-specialist audience, supporting awareness-raising at European level.

3.2.2 Project partner videos

In the final period of the project, a series of project partner videos have been produced to highlight the diversity of expertise within the project consortium and to humanize the project by showcasing the people behind the R&D&I activities. The videos were structured as short interviews with representatives from different project partners.

Each project partner video provides:

- A brief introduction to the organization,
- An overview of the project partner's role and key tasks within the EM-TECH project,
- Reflections on the main benefits and learning outcomes gained through the participation,
- Perspectives on future plans and potential follow-up activities after the end of the project.

This format supports transparent and relatable communication by presenting the EM-TECH project from multiple viewpoints, strengthening stakeholder engagement and increasing trust, identification with the project, and its outcomes.

3.2.3 Final Webinar Series

The final webinar series has been organized as a central communication activity to present the overall EM-TECH project journey and achievements after 36 months of R&D&I activities. As illustrated in Figure 2 the series consisted of four webinars, jointly covering ten key POs.

The banner features a dark blue background with a large circular image of a dark green electric car charging at a station in a lush, green environment. The text 'Final Webinar Series' is prominently displayed in white and green. Below it, the text 'Join our webinars to hear all about EM-TECH's project results' is written in white. A calendar icon indicates the dates: Friday, 21.11.2025, 28.11.2025, 5.12.2025, and 12.12.2025. A clock icon shows the time: 11:00 am - 12 am CET. A 'Register Now' button is located at the bottom right. Logos for '2e ZERO' and 'Funded by the European Union' are in the top right corner. At the bottom, there are links to follow on LinkedIn and visit the website www.emtechproject.eu. A small disclaimer at the bottom left states: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101096083. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.'

Figure 2: Final Webinar Series promoting visual

The format allowed the project to communicate its achievements in a structured and narrative-driven manner, highlighting the evolution of the work carried out, the key messages, and the overall contribution of the EM-TECH project.

The final webinar series served as a unifying communication moment at the end of the project, consolidating key messages, celebrating achievements, and providing a clear and understandable overview of EM-TECH's results and legacy. The session recordings are made available on the project website: <https://emtechproject.eu/webinar/>

3.3 Assessment of communication activities

To provide an overview of the performed communication activities, they have been categorized by the type of communication activity and illustrated in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Type of communication activity

A thorough assessment of the conducted communication activities based on the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) according to the grant agreement (including the sections web channels, public media, events and actions on consortium level, and events and actions at community level) will be included in EM-TECH's final reporting.

4 Project dissemination

Dissemination is a proactive process of making project results publicly available to maximize their impact within and beyond the EU. It aims to ensure that the advancements, knowledge, and data generated within the EU-funded R&D projects are shared systematically with the targeted audiences such as researchers, industry, policymakers, and the public at large. In this way, dissemination supports transparency and visibility of the project results and in general sets a stage for science.

The performed dissemination activities are aligned with the project’s objectives, expected results, and impact pathways, and are carried out throughout the project lifecycle as results matured. Attention has been given to the selection of appropriate formats and channels to reach specialized audiences and to support the uptake and potential reuse of EM-TECH’s POs.

All dissemination actions have been conducted in accordance with Horizon Europe principles, including open science practices where applicable, and have been coordinated across the project consortium to ensure consistency, quality, and relevance. The following subsections outline the dissemination highlights of EM-TECH and provide an overview of the dissemination activities performed over the entire project duration.

4.1 Highlights

A couple of dissemination activities have been selected to be included in this highlights section.

4.1.1 TRA conference

The Transport Research Arena (TRA) conference is Europe’s largest research and technology conference on transport and mobility—covering all major categories of transport (road, rail, air, and water) and addressing passenger & freight transport, urban mobility, and inter-urban mobility, but also innovative policies and the latest technological developments. Co-organized by the European Commission, the TRA was first held in 2006 and takes place every two years in different European cities. The TRA connects research with industry, policymakers and other stakeholders to accelerate developments and transitions of the future transport system in Europe and beyond. [1]

The 10th edition of the TRA was held on April 15-18, 2024, in Dublin (4000+ attendees, 150+ exhibitors) and EM-TECH engaging with multiple activities. The joint paper (with contribution of the HighScape project) by Weinzerl et al. [2] entitled “Innovative E-Motor Technologies for E-Axles and E-Corners Vehicle Architectures Enabling Highly Efficient and Sustainable E-Mobility” was presented by Eric Armengaud and Bo Wang. The EM-TECH project has also contributed to an E-VOLVE cluster paper and poster entitled “E-VOLVE Cluster: Increasing Innovation Efficiency to Support the Transition Toward Sustainable e-mobility.” by Armengaud et al. [3]. Moreover, the EM-TECH project was represented at the EARPA stand (AIG, USR) and at the Innovate UK stand (UBATH), including a 3D printed prototype of the e-gear.

4.1.2 RTR conference

The Road Transport Research (RTR) conference in Brussels is organized by the European Commission (EC), European Road Transport Research Advisory Council (ERTRAC), European Green Vehicle Initiative Association for the 2Zero partnership (EGVIAfor2Zero), Cooperative, Connected & Automated Mobility (CCAM) Association, and Batteries European Partnership Association (BEPA), among others. This

conference is the main European forum for the dissemination of intermediate and final project results of publicly funded road-transport-based R&D projects. The EM-TECH project has received an Invitation for Presentation in 2024 (approx. 735 participants), 2025 (900+), and even for 2026 (500+ expected), providing the opportunity to showcase the project’s achievements to a broad set of stakeholders, bridging the gap between research and real-world implementation, and finally, contributing to European future mobility solutions. [4]

4.1.3 SAE WCX™

The SAE World Congress Experience (WCX™) is an annual global mobility event with a broad technical scope organized by SAE International, bringing together engineers, researchers, OEMs, suppliers, policymakers, and other stakeholders to exchange knowledge, showcase research, development, and innovation, discuss trends, and shape the future of mobility. TUIL in the person of Valentin Ivanov co-organized a special session at the SAE WCX in 2024 and 2025. Moreover, the EM-TECH project contributed to the 2025 edition of the SAE WCX with two papers, namely Caponio et al. [6] and Armengaud et al. [7].

4.1.4 Journal publications

During the three years of project duration a couple of publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals have been achieved or about to be published. The publishing journals are Mechanism and Machine Theory (Impact Factor 5.3, CiteScore 11.4), IEEE Access (3.6, 9.0), IEEE Transactions and Industry Applications (5.4, 9.7), and SAE International Journal of Advances and Current Practices in Mobility (1.7, 0.4).

4.2 Assessment of dissemination activities

Figure 4 provides an overview of the performed dissemination activities, which have been categorized by the type of dissemination activity.

Figure 4: Type of dissemination activity

In terms of publications, Figure 5 provides some quantitative insights into EM-TECH’s publications and distinguishes between the different types of publications.

Figure 5: Type of publication

An in-depth assessment of the accomplished dissemination activities based on the KPIs according to the grant agreement (including the sections representation/innovation presentations, open access publications, professional societies platforms, and advocate ecosystem platforms) will be included in EM-TECH's final report.

5 Project exploitation

With exploitation the EM-TECH project strives for utilization of project results, creating value and impact for the public at large and the involved projects partners while supporting current EU policies and roadmaps. The project results are setting up an avenue for further research, product development, standardization, or policymaking, extending the project’s influence beyond its duration. The following subsections outline (i) the project partners’ currently planned exploitation pathways, (ii) EM-TECH’s exploitation activities including an assessment, and (iii) the created VPCs and BMCs.

5.1 Project partners’ exploitation pathways

To collect information about the intended exploitation pathways from all project partners, an online survey with 30 questions has been developed utilizing Microsoft Forms. More details are provided in an extra document, the sensitive appendix to deliverable D7.3. The following paragraphs provide an anonymous overview over a couple of topics addressed in the survey.

Rating of the exploitation result: The project partners rated the exploitation results in respect to the innovativeness, relevance, impact, and exploitability, which the result being shown in Figure 6 below. The rating shows no low or very low rating for innovativeness, relevance, and impact, and just one low rating for exploitability. At the same time, exploitability received the most very high ratings with 50% of the total ratings.

Figure 6: Rating of the exploitation result (Innovativeness / Relevance / Impact / Exploitability)

Connection to other R&D projects and/or strategic alliances: Five project partners reported the connection to other R&D projects, whereas two mentioned internal development potential and possible exploitation routes, and five outlined options for further R&D projects or other research activities.

Description of the market addressed: The responses on the market description received range from the automotive (OEMs, Tier-1 Suppliers) over maritime, rail, agriculture sector, to technology innovators in general.

Potential early adopters, first friendly customers: All project partners except two have already concrete stakeholder segments under consideration to reach out to first.

Expected commercial/scientific/socio-economic impact: Eight out of ten project partners expect a commercial impact, nine out of ten expect a scientific impact from the exploitable result, whereas only seven project partners have identified a socio-economic impact.

Impact on collaborative partners: Except of one project partner all have reported a positive impact due to the collaboration in the EM-TECH project.

Availability of results: Four out of ten project partners reported having at least partially open-source results.

Intellectual Property Right (IPR) type pursued: Figure 7 outlines the reply on the multi-choice question about the IPR type pursued.

Figure 7: Feedback on pursued IPR type

5.2 Assessment of exploitation activities

Figure 8 provides an overview of the performed exploitation activities based on a categorization of the type of exploitation activity.

Figure 8: Type of exploitation activity

A comprehensive assessment of the achieved exploitation activities based on the grant agreements' KPIs (including the sections Intellectual Property (IP) protection and patenting of EM-TECH assets, industrial and research showcasing, and exploitation through beneficiaries) will be included in EM-TECH's final reporting.

5.3 Value Proposition Canvas

The VPC is a widely adopted strategic tool designed to help organizations to (a) “understand the patterns of value creation,” (b) “leverage the experience and skills of your team,” and (c) “avoid wasting time with ideas that won’t work.” This framework is based upon the BMC’s two building blocks “Value Proposition” and “Customer Segments”, creating the Customer Profile and the Value Map, as well as achieving a “fit” between them. The “Customer Profile” captures the characteristics of specific customer segments by investigating (1) tasks the customers try to perform or problems they would like to solve (called “customer jobs”), (2) negative experiences, risks, or obstacles related to the customer jobs (“pains”), and (3) desired outcomes or benefits that customers seek for (“gains”). The “Value Map” reflects the “Products & Services” offered, “pain relievers” that alleviate the customers pains, and “gain creators” that generate desired customers benefits. [8] The following paragraphs briefly describe the VPCs of the respective project partner, whereas the detailed VPCs can be found in the appendix.

AVL’s customer profile reveals a strong need for advanced, sustainable e-motor solutions focused on circularity and reduced rare-earth content dependency. Customers aim to adopt next-generation electric motors and require thorough testing and validation. The project addresses key pains such as high costs for magnets containing rare-earth content and lengthy validation cycles, mitigated through AVL’s project coordination and oversight. While AVL does not provide direct technical input, it creates an enabling environment for project partners to deliver gains. Under AVL’s guidance, EM-TECH develops high-performance, efficient, and circular motor technologies supported by advanced simulation and transparent lifecycle assessments. Knowledge exchange and alignment with industry standards further reinforce the value proposition.

TUIL’s value map is centered on its strong automotive engineering expertise, particularly in powertrain and vehicle control systems. TUIL addresses key customer pains such as lacking accuracy between the simulation and real-world performance through advanced XiL-based co-simulation testing environments. These capabilities enable robust interfaces that effectively align the operation of controllers and the involved models. Next-generation electric vehicle (EV) component development is one of TUIL’s gain creators, leading to EVs utilizing cutting-edge components and consequently improving the vehicle’s energy-efficiency, performance, and sustainability. The aforementioned gain creators and the real-time capable HiL and XiL testing environments are resulting in collaborations and (European) R&D projects with leading technical universities and industrial companies, while addressing their customer jobs. TUIL’s education and training programs in the e-mobility ecosystem together with their ambition in R&D programs is leading to an excellent breeding ground for knowledge transfer and workforce development.

POLITO’s products & services are focused on the complexities of developing highly efficient and sustainable e-mobility solutions, enabled by the utilization of simulation models, LCA and LCC methods, and state-of-the-art testing environments. POLITO’s specialized knowledge in electric motor technology and e-mobility such as the temperature estimation in IWMs mitigates the customer’s pain of limited access to specialized and innovative research and the challenges faced in the development of sustainable and integrated e-mobility solutions. The gains created in the context of international R&D projects include detailed simulation models and digital twins, intelligent cooling circuit design, and the utilization of LCA and LCC for IWMs and AFMs, leading to joint research and international collaboration, accelerated

development lifecycles of next-generation e-mobility solutions, and potential cost reductions. Herewith, POLITO addresses customer jobs including the design and implementation of next-generation e-mobility solutions, sustainability assessment in compliance with policies in force, monitoring and controlling of electric motors, and testing and validating advanced electrified powertrain prototypes.

ELA's focuses on the development of IWMs, leading to automotive engineering services and capabilities for e-drive design, evaluation, and integration, novel control strategies for IWMs, and in general IP established around IWMs. ELA's pain relievers contain among others the compact, modular, and simply integration of the developed e-drive system, reduced rare earth content dependency, and overall improvement of energy-efficiency and cost, mitigate the customer's concerns including energy losses in conventional systems, space requirements, lack of modularity, and integration of complex e-drive technology. Moreover, ELA provides the customers with greater design freedom with IWMs, competitive and innovative e-drive technology coming along with multiple new opportunities, and insights into the system requirements. ELA's customers strive for the integration of energy-efficient e-drive systems, reduction of efforts and time for integration, control strategies of the IWM, and the fulfilment of the needs of the OEM.

I&M's customers request certification of electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) for their components or modules, energy loss reduction, partnerships supporting innovation and compliance with EU standards, design of high-performance e-drive systems including embedded software and system on chip (SoC) design, and rapid prototyping. I&M's products & services contain high-performance hardware tailored for e-drive systems, generation of detailed models and digital twins, and design of automotive inverters, resulting in a couple of gain creators and pain relievers. I&M relieves the pain points associated with technology validation, SoC on full-system level, and cogging torque. Moreover, with cost-effective inverter/motor platforms and novel control strategies I&M creates significant gains, including performance and energy-efficiency of the e-drive system beyond the EU targets, lower rare earth content demand, and EMC certification.

URBANGOLD's products & services address implementation of proprietary technologies for efficient processing of challenging materials, development of design and recycling processes, and investigation of potential environmental impacts and economic evolution of IWMs. By applying innovative technologies, considering environmental standards and circular economy targets, and offering data-driven projections, URBANGOLD tackles the customer's pains on lack of standardized tools/methods to compare EV-related technologies, their necessity to comply with environmental standards, and for standardization compliance, and recycling difficulties for e-waste. By publishing articles, providing recommendations, promoting recycling initiatives, raising awareness, and establishing networks, URBANGOLD achieves substantial gains, including positioning of themselves as leaders in recycling of electric motors, obtaining access to advanced processes for efficient metal recovery, and increasing market credibility.

AIG's value proposition is based on the products & services such as innovation management, strategy development, CDE planning, and technical integration management for R&D, leading to CDE of sustainable and impactful project results, enhanced project visibility, stakeholder engagement, and alignment of technical and economic targets. These gain creators and pain relievers enable AIG's customers to accomplish great visibility for the project activities, manage difficulties in multi-stakeholder R&D projects,

and handle challenges in aligning technical innovations with market needs. Finally, AIG's addresses their customer's jobs, such as implementing innovation strategies, management of project lifecycles, effective CDE of project results, and management of ongoing processes in running projects.

USR's products & services are focused on vehicle dynamics and control, extensive research facilities, simulation models and virtual/experimental validation methodologies, and the hardware required for rapid prototyping, enabling advanced electric motor development. Their expertise in control strategy design, simulation, and component testing—such as hardware-in-the-loop (HiL) testing environments—supports concurrent evaluation of hardware and software in early-stages of the development process, reducing development risks and boosting competitiveness. USR also drives R&D&I in control strategies for IWMs and onboard AFMs, addressing the lack of early vehicle-level product assessment. Beyond technology, USR fosters collaboration, provides access to cutting-edge research, and enhances future engineers' employability through practical, real-world engagement.

UBATH's value proposition focuses on design and simulation, full hardware prototype development of the innovative e-gear, and the experimental validation at component and module level. The e-gear provides enhanced adaptability and energy-efficiency of the IWM, greater torque and power density that enables smaller design, which are finally solving the strict space constraints. Moreover, UBATH embeds environmental considerations from early design stages onward, which is together with the applied simulation environment leading to adoption of recycled materials and designs promoting circular economy, faster validation via digital twins and virtual sensing, and shortened development processes in general. With these approaches performance and sustainability related development goals can be achieved simultaneously, laying the foundation for efficient, innovative, and environmentally responsible e-mobility solutions from collaborative R&D&I actions.

TRX's focuses on the design, development, and prototype production of yokeless AFMs with superior torque and power density, high energy-efficiency, and improved cooling concepts. TRX addresses their customers' need for innovative electric motor technologies to be integrated into various existing EV architectures while fulfilling the Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) targets and complying with current regulations. TRX tackles the challenges in achieving high performance within limited space while maintaining reliability and reducing rare-earth content demands—a key EM-TECH requirement. TRX is committed to improving the performance and sustainability of onboard AFMs simultaneously, ensuring compliance with the ESG targets, and reaching out for collaborative research, positioning TRX as a key contributor for AFMs in next-generation e-mobility solutions.

5.4 Business Model Canvas

The BMC is a well-known graphical framework utilized in strategic management and innovation management, representing information of *“how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value”*. The nine building blocks of the BMC consist of: *“Customer Segments, Value Proposition, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure.”* [9] Its simplicity and integrative perspective make the BMC distinctive, enabling people to collaboratively map information, critically reflect the organization's business model, and iteratively adopt thoughts or assumptions whenever needed. The BMC's visual nature supports cross-disciplinary

understanding among the people involved, which is particularly important for complex and uncertain environments. This framework helps to systematically analyze and innovate business models, identify risks, and make strategic decisions based on organizational capabilities which are aligned with the customer needs.

In the context of R&D projects, the BMC is especially useful for exploitation and impact strategy development, as it supports the transition of project results into viable business applications. The BMCs from all EM-TECH project partners can be found in the appendix, including all statements gathered and to be interpreted straightforward. Furthermore, the BMC supports to better align technological innovation with market demand, society needs, or political/regulatory roadmaps, thereby increasing the likelihood of sustainable impact beyond the duration of the EM-TECH project.

6 Sustainability concept

This section outlines the project’s long-term exploitation strategy, providing a comprehensive concept to ensure sustained use, valorization, and impact of the POs beyond the project duration. Communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities performed during the project are translated into concrete long-term opportunities for market uptake, further research, and policy refinement. A synthesis of these activities is presented in the next subsection, followed by concise one pager reflecting the POs, both showcasing potential pathways for utilization. Finally, a PESTEL analysis and Porter’s Five Forces assessment is conducted to gain a better understanding of the respective industry. Together, these elements provide a strategic basis for maximizing the project’s long-term impact in alignment with the EU’s innovation and sustainability objectives.

6.1 One Pagers

To increase visibility and outreach for the POs, One Pagers have been created, published via Zenodo, and communicated on the EM-TECH LinkedIn page. In total, nine One Pagers have been created. In Figure 9 the One Pager of PO2 entitled “High power density axial flux motor prototype” is illustrated to provide an example. More details can be found in Table 2.

HIGH POWER DENSITY AXIAL FLUX MOTOR PROTOTYPE

TRAXIAL *i&m* AVL EM-TECH

Higher power density with lower rare earth dependency Cost-efficient design ready for scalable high volume production Compact, modular architecture adaptable to multiple vehicle platforms

THE CHALLENGE: developing an axial flux motor with two traditionally conflicting objectives — achieving higher power density while reducing rare earth materials. In typical motor design, engineers face a trade-off: more power density requires more rare earth magnets. This posed a significant technical hurdle.

THE SOLUTION: TRAXIAL’s engineering team successfully developed an innovative axial flux motor prototype that achieves both objectives. The team created a compact, modular design adaptable for different vehicle applications, providing Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs)—companies that build vehicles—with a viable solution for electric drivetrain development. Having conquered the core technical challenge, TRAXIAL’s engineers focused on practical manufacturability for real-world production. The team successfully integrated advanced manufacturing techniques including plastic laser welding and stator overmolding into the prototype design. Their work proved these processes effective for volume production scenarios while reducing material usage and simplifying manufacturing procedure.

KEY BENEFITS:

- Enhanced Power Density - Prototype achieves improved performance per unit weight and volume
- Reduced Rare Earth Dependency - Significant reduction in rare earth material requirements while maintaining performance
- Manufacturing Readiness - Advanced production processes suitable for scalable manufacturing

IMPACT AND NEXT STEPS: The EM-TECH axial flux motor demonstrates that high power density and sustainability can coexist. By cutting rare earth usage and enabling cost-efficient mass production, TRAXIAL’s solution supports greener mobility while strengthening Europe’s supply chain resilience.

Prototype validation in real-world environments, followed by integration with advanced inverters and e-axle systems during the project confirmed the performance targets and prepare the technology for industrialization. With this foundation, TRAXIAL is ready to bring a new generation of sustainable, high-performance electric drivetrains to the market.

Figure 1: Axial flux motor

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LinkedIn emtechproject.eu

Figure 9: Exemplary One Pager

Table 2: Overview of the One Pagers

No.	PO	Title of the One Payer	Involved project partners
1	PO1, PO3	<i>Innovative in-wheel motor design with integrated direct cooling and mechanical e-gear</i>	ELA, POLITO
2	PO2	<i>High power density axial flux motor prototype</i>	TRX, I&M, AVL
3	PO2	<i>High power density axial flux on-board motor and drive series</i>	POLITO
4	PO4, PO5	<i>Virtual sensing for electric motor and inverter control</i>	POLITO, I&M
5	PO6	<i>Technology for using recycled permanent magnets</i>	URBANGOLD
6	PO7	<i>Electric drive controllers</i>	USR, TUIL
7	PO8	<i>Digital twinning framework for electric drive design</i>	USR, AVL, TUIL
8	PO9	<i>Electric drive LCA & LCC methodology for engineering services</i>	POLITO, AVL
9	PO10	<i>Distributed XiL testing methodology</i>	POLITO, AVL, TUIL, USR, UBATH

6.2 PESTEL analysis

The strategic analysis tool PESTEL is used to identify and evaluate macro-environmental factors that can affect an organization’s performance and strategic decision making. The acronym PESTEL stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal factors, each representing a category of external influences that shape the broader business environment. Among others, often used variants of the acronym PESTEL are PEST and PESTLE, or the newest acronym extension being PESTELE by adding the ethical factor. This analysis enables organizations or in this context the EM-TECH project to anticipate the macro-environment, identify threats and opportunities, respond proactively, and finally gain a competitive advantage. [10] The following paragraphs provide an overview of external influences on the EM-TECH project:

Political: EC’s Horizon Europe funding program aligns the approved projects with the industrial and climate roadmaps/policies in force, enabling financial and strategic advantages for contributing organizations, reputational development, and networking benefits. With their greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction targets and the transition towards clean mobility, the EC is creating political momentum and market pull for electric traction technologies with the Paris Agreement [11], European Green Deal [12], “Fit for 55” package [13], 2Zero SRIA [14], CCAM SRIA 2021-2027 [15], Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy [16], and the recently presented Automotive Package [17].

Economic: The International Energy Agency’s annually released Global EV Outlook reports a continuously growing EV market, as shown by the global EV sales in Figure 10. EV sales reached more than 17 million units in 2024, an increase by more than 25% or 3.5 million units compared to the year 2023, which is more than the total number of EV sold in 2020. [18]

Figure 10: Global EV sales from 2014 to 2024 [18]

Moreover, EV market growth expands the total addressable market for EM-TECH’s both electric motors typologies, AFMs and IWMs. For electric motors the cost in €/kW is an important metric, which is explicitly targeted in the EM-TECH project (AFMs: 5 €/kW, IWMs: <6 €/kW). This metric is leveraged by increased power density, reduced rare earth content demand, design-for-manufacturing approach, and economies of scale, finally improving the components competitiveness. Moreover, raw material costs in general, volatility of energy prices, uncertainties in the supply chain, and inflation are impacting the bill of material (BOM) costs as well. Nowadays risk management, supply chain resilience (especially regarding rare earth magnets), and EV’s price forecasting are becoming increasingly important and highly localized, influencing the organization’s margin and finally the success of their business. [19],[20]

Social: Rising sustainability expectations from consumers and corporations drive demand for low-carbon electric motors, which are designed with consideration of recycling aspects. Consequently, the need for comprehensive LCAs and stricter reporting requirements is increasing [21]. Urbanization and fleet electrification reshape vehicle usage patterns, pushing technology choices toward compact, high-torque AFM and IWM applications [22]. Digitalization and advanced e-motor development increase demand for specialized skills in motor design, digital twins, and control systems, creating recruitment and training pressures for organizations [23]. Finally, the uptake of EVs leads to improved air quality and reduced premature mortality in connection with particulate matter [24].

Technological: With onboard AFMs and radial flux IWMs two emerging motor typologies are investigated and further enhanced in the EM-TECH project, but there are also other motor typologies, such as the Switched Reluctance Motors (SRMs) or Interior Permanent Magnet Synchronous Reluctance Motors (IPM SynRMs). OEMs and suppliers of electric motors have rare earth content reduction strategies in place, limiting the dependence on rare earth content and reducing costs. Key factors driving R&D in the field of electric motors are installation space reduction, performance improvements, optimizations of the cooling

concepts or thermal management, controllability, power electronics, and reduction of rare earth content demand. [19],[25] Innovation cycles in the automotive industry are getting faster, leading to the need for continuous assessment of currently applied technology but also technology scouting and foresight.

Environmental: Circular design of electric motors and its LCA is becoming increasingly important in the EU, leading to a big carbon footprint decrease by making the electric motor production (Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 emissions) more environmentally friendly, considering design-for-disassembly to increase the recycling ratio of the most crucial materials, such as critical raw materials (CRM) used in permanent magnets. The CRM Act aims to ensure resilient and sustainable supply of CRM. [21],[26] Additionally, energy-efficiency improvements of electric motors lead to an increased driving range of EVs, which supports the adoption of EV in the public at large and reduces GHG emissions.

Legal: EVs and its components must comply with a set of regulations and directives, such as the vehicle type-approval under Regulation (EU) 2018/858 [27], the Low Voltage Directive (LVD) [28], or United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) Regulation No. 10 on EMC of electrical and electronic components in the vehicle [29]. In the context of joint R&D projects, like the EM-TECH project, it is essential to have valuable POs secured by patents or an IP protection strategy. [30] Finally, whenever data is collected, processed, utilized, or monetized, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [31] must be considered.

6.3 Porter's Five Forces

This framework created back in 1979 is still state-of-the-art and includes five forces, which must be investigated to better understand an industry's competition. Those five forces are described shortly as follows: [32][33]

Bargaining power of suppliers: Suppliers influence costs, quality, and availability of critical products or services. In case there are just a few suppliers (e.g., permanent magnets for electric motors) or a supplier provides a unique product or service, their bargaining power increases. Consequently, this can lead to higher prices or supply constraints, impacting on the manufacturer's margin and/or the final retail price.

Bargaining power of customers: Customer strengthen their bargaining power when they have multiple purchase options, purchase in large quantities, or face low switching costs. OEMs might force electric motor manufacturers to provide price discounts, better performance figures, or improved sustainability. High bargaining power of customers is pushing innovation and resulting in competitive pricing.

Threat of new entrants: New entrants can disrupt the market by introducing innovative technologies or cost advantages. Required R&D expenses or IP protection are two examples of entry barriers to the electric motor market, which are mainly influencing the level of this threat.

Threat of substitute products or services: Substitute products or technologies significantly reduce the demand for currently existing products or services. For electric traction motors a substitute would be for example internal combustion engines. The risk of substitution influences the pricing of products or services, as organizations might be forced to perform countermeasures by differentiation through performance or other metrics of the product or service.

Rivalry: This force reflects the intensity of competition among current companies in an industry. Factors influencing the level of rivalry are e.g., number of competitors, market growth, fixed costs, or missing differentiation. In the market for electric traction motors, the level of rivalry is affected by technological advancements and regulations/directives, among others.

Figure 11 illustrates the Porter’s Five Forces framework. For the utilization of Porter’s Five Forces the EM-TECH project partners have been split into two groups: (1) public/academic project partners (POLITO, TUIL, UBATH, USR) and (2) industry project partner (AIG, AVL, ELA, I&M, TRX, URBANGOLD). Porter’s Five Forces has been conducted for both groups separately and is described in the following two subsections.

Figure 11: Forces governing competition in an industry [33]

The strength of each force was identified by assessing each argument listed for the respective force with a score from the scoring table outlined in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Scoring table

Score	Description
2	Strongly increases the force
1	Moderately increases the force
0	Neutral
-1	Moderately weakens the force
-2	Strongly weakens the force

The scores of all arguments of the respective force have been summed up to a total score, and the final mapping has been conducted based on the force strength mapping outlined in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Force strength mapping

Total score	Description
≥ 6	Very strong
2 to 5	Strong
-1 to 1	Moderate
-5 to -2	Weak
≤ -6	Very weak

6.3.1 Bargaining power of suppliers

The bargaining power of suppliers is based on threatening the organization with higher prices or lower quality of the products or services offered. A strong bargaining power of suppliers influences achievable margins in a market, if the affected organization cannot pass on the increased costs. The bargaining power of supplier depends on the number of suppliers, threat of substitute products or services, importance of the market for the supplier, relevance of the product or service for the customer, among others. The arguments identified for both groups in the context of the EM-TECH project are listed and assessed in Table 5.

Table 5: Arguments related to the bargaining power of suppliers

Arguments (public/academic group)	Score	Arguments (industry group)	Score
Funding bodies and their research grants	2	Geographic concentration of rare earth processing	2
Specialized laboratory equipment supplier	1	Semiconductor supply chain vulnerability	1
Lock-in from CAE software supplier	1	Price volatility of CRM	1
Talent acquisition	1	EU CRM Act	-1
Material limitations	0	Lock-in from software & CAE suppliers	2
TOTAL	5	Scarce specialized test labs	1
		Contract manufacturing variability	0
		Magnet recycling emergence	-1
		TOTAL	5

The bargaining power of supplier is strong for the public/academic group mainly because the laboratories and testing environment are highly dependent on funding bodies and their research grants as well as the very specialized laboratory equipment needed to operate them at full capacity. Due to (1) geographical concentration of rare earth processing, (2) high switching costs for the fully integrated software solutions creating a lock-in situation, and (3) the uncertainty of semiconductor supply, the bargaining power of suppliers is strong for the industry group too.

6.3.2 Bargaining power of customers

The customers may reduce the margin of a single organization or the entire market, especially by claiming price reductions, higher quality, or greater performance. The bargaining power of customers depends on the number of customers, high ratio of product/service costs to total costs of the customer, or low switching costs, among others. The arguments identified for both groups in the context of the EM-TECH project are listed and assessed in Table 6.

Table 6: Arguments related to the bargaining power of customers

Arguments (public/academic group)	Score	Arguments (industry group)	Score
Industrial partners influence areas of research	2	OEMs purchasing strategies	2
Funding agencies dictate research priorities	2	Public funding and procurement requirements	1
Policy directives impact areas of research	1	Differentiation through unique products or services	-1
Collaboration with peers	-1	Long co-development cycles	-1
Laboratory uniqueness	-1	Powerful role of Tier-1 Suppliers	1
TOTAL	3	Cost focus of OEMs/Tier1-Suppliers	2
		Fleet operators focusing on TCO and sustainability	0
		TOTAL	4

EM-TECH's industrial customers are representing the demand in the market and funding agencies have the power to dictate the priority of research areas in terms of available grants. Both arguments strongly increase the bargaining power of customers, whereas collaboration with other academic institutions and the unique experimental capabilities of laboratories moderate it slightly. Finally, the bargaining power of customers for the public/academic group has been assessed as strong. Due to (1) the large orders, detailed specifications, and strict timelines from OEMs and (2) the OEM's strict vehicle target price and the limited number of suppliers to the OEM, the bargaining power of customers is strong for the industry group too.

6.3.3 Threat of new entrants

This threat mainly depends on entry barriers such as economies of scale, capital intensity, accessibility (of testing facilities, R&D consortia, expertise, and professional networks), and regulations, standards, roadmaps, and directives. Low barriers raise the threat of new entrants. The arguments identified for both groups in the context of the EM-TECH project are listed and assessed in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Arguments related to the threat of new entrants

Arguments (public/academic group)	Score	Arguments (industry group)	Score
Laboratory and testing infrastructure	-2	Capex and Test benches	-2
Access to project grant and consortium	-2	Regulations (UNECE, ISO), Homologation	-1
Specialized expertise	-2	Multi-physics model and validation	-2
Reputation and professional network	-1	Access to OEMs/Tier-1 Suppliers	-1
Digital and Open Access tools	1	Access to materials supply	-1
Horizon Europe joint-labs	1	Talent shortage	-1
TOTAL	-5	Economies of scale and cost targets	-2
		CAE open-source tools	2
		Horizon Europe funding	1
		Software-only niche entrants	1
		TOTAL	-6

Potential new entrants face high entry barriers, especially concerning (1) the required specialized laboratory and testing infrastructure, (2) the ability to secure national/international research grants, and (3) acquisition of highly skilled employees and their expertise, leading to a weak threat of new entrants for the public/academic group. For the industry group on the other side, especially (1) the high capital expenditures for test benches, pilot production lines, and prototyping, (2) the necessity of managing complex multi-physics models and the capability of designing and controlling AFMs and IWMs, and (3) accomplishing the ambitious cost targets, raises the entry barrier of other organizations. CAE tools that are available as open-source solutions are an example that lowers the entry barrier. Finally, the threat of new entrants for the industry group is very weak.

6.3.4 Threat of substitute products or services

Substitutes are products or services that perform the same function as the product or service of an industry. The arguments identified for both groups in the context of the EM-TECH project are listed and assessed in Table 8 below.

Table 8: Arguments related to the threat of substitute products or services

Arguments (public/academic group)	Score	Arguments (industry group)	Score
Other academic laboratories	1	Alternative propulsion systems	-1
OEM increases in-house capabilities	2	Proven commodity electric motor	1
Increasing utilization of simulation and modelling	1	Improvements in power electronics and control algorithms	1
Shared open datasets	0	Outsourcing of engineering	1
Emerging joint-lab structures	-1	Software-only approach	1
TOTAL	3	Circularity and Recycling	-1
		TOTAL	2

The public/academic group is facing a strong threat of substitute products or services, mainly because of the OEMs shifting to increase their in-house laboratory and R&D capabilities, which are on a competitive level with the academic laboratories. For the industry group the threat of substitute products or services is moderate, as there are only moderate influences on this threat. This includes substitution options like (1) well-proven electric motors with different motor typology, (2) technological enhancement in power electronics and motor control algorithms can reduce the risks and costs in contrast to the adoption of novel motor typologies, and (3) circularity and recycling can shift demand and product economics, although this is not a direct product substitution.

6.3.5 Rivalry among current competitors

The rivalry among current competitors is influenced by the number of competitors, growth of the industry, high fixed costs, missing differentiation, high switch costs, and high exit barriers, among others. The arguments identified for both groups in the context of the EM-TECH project are listed and assessed in Table 9 below.

Table 9: Arguments related to rivalry

Arguments (public/academic group)	Score	Arguments (industry group)	Score
High number of universities and academic institutions	2	Large engineering companies	2
Competition for research grants	2	CAE suppliers	2
Corporate internal competition	1	Niche SMEs	0
Fewer automotive R&D projects available	1	OEMs increasingly perform R&D in-house	1
Shift to collaboration for increased visibility	-1	Rapid technology lifecycles	1
Dynamics due to R&D projects	1	Dynamics due to R&D projects	1
TOTAL	6	TOTAL	7

The rivalry among current competitors is very strong for the public/academic group, mainly because of the (1) high number of universities, academic institutions, or research and technology organizations, and (2) high national/international competition for research grants. For the industry group the rivalry is very strong too, influenced by (1) large engineering companies with established customer relationships, global presence, and big capital, and (2) software supplier, which are blurring the lines between physical, hybrid, and pure virtual testing environments.

6.3.6 Overview and concluding statement

EM-TECH’s macro-environment and the electric traction motor market is a highly competitive market to be entered. An overview of the assessment of the five forces for both groups is provided by Table 10 below.

Table 10: Assessment overview of Porter’s Five Forces

Forces	Assessment of public/academic group	Assessment of industry group
Bargaining power of suppliers	Strong (5)	Strong (5)
Bargaining power of customers	Strong (3)	Strong (4)
Threat of new entrants	Weak (-5)	Very weak (-6)
Threat of substitute products or services	Strong (3)	Moderate (2)
Rivalry among current competitors	Very strong (6)	Very strong (7)

6.4 Market situation, roadmaps, and trends of the automotive ecosystem

The information provided in the following paragraphs of this subsection is part and a direct citation of the research paper in press by Ratz et al. [34], which has been submitted to the TRA 2026 in Budapest, Hungary, resulting from joint activities in the E-VOLVE cluster and the ten R&D projects involved:

“Shrinking of European market share: Electrification and digitalization have markedly increased complexity of the automotive ecosystem by reshaping global value chains, restructuring of the suppliers’ roles, and rising numbers of new entrants mixing up the market situation on both vehicle and component level. (Ramos & Ruiz-Gálvez, 2024; Jagani et al., 2024) The EU automotive industry generated over 7 % of EU’s total gross domestic product (equivalent to € 1,256.0 billion for 2024), employed around 13.8 million people, and strongly

affected its upstream and downstream industries. In 2024 the EU motor vehicle production reached only 13.8 million passenger cars (14.9 % of the global production), leading to a substantial reduction in the EU of 7.25 % compared to the previous year. The globally leading vehicle manufacturer has changed over the last years, with Greater China expanding their leading position (34 % in 2024, 28 % in 2019, 23 % in 2009) in contrast to the runner-up Europe (19 % in 2024, 23 % in 2019, 27 % in 2009). (Statista, 2025; ACEA, 2025) The global automotive industry reached a market size of USD 4,359.98 billion in 2024 and is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 5.66 % from 2024 to 2032, reaching an estimated market size of USD 6,678.28 billion by 2032 (FinTech Futures, 2024) and primarily propelled by the world's increasing demand for EVs (IEA, 2025).” [34]

“EV market dominated by Asia: Thus, it is imperative to scrutinize the EV market itself and the market situation of its required EV specific components. In 2024 the global EV market size achieved USD 890.72 billion with 17 million units sold, which is 25 % more EVs sold in contrast to the previous year. More than every fifth new car sold worldwide is being electric and the Aisa Pacific region dominating the global EV market with a market of 49 % in 2024. The predicted 2025 global EV market size of USD 988.7 billion has been forecasted to USD 2,529.1 billion by 2034 at a CAGR of 11 %. (Precedence Research, 2025; IEA, 2025) The EV adoption and EV market growth is accelerated by multiple factors, including (a) governmental initiatives or policies (e.g., tax rebates, subsidies and grants, benefits in the registration and operation of EVs), (b) rigorous environmental regulations and aggressive governmental promotions, (c) technological advancements of EVs on vehicle and component level (e.g., battery technology, efficiency and recyclability of EV specific components like the electric traction motors, affordability of EV), (d) the customer's demand for user-friendly, safer, and more sustainable vehicles, as well as (e) the improvement of the charging infrastructure, highlighting the crucial role of EVs for the future of the entire automotive industry to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, improve the travelling experience, and operational expenditures. The market size for EV traction motors reached USD 12.57 billion with Aisa Pacific being the dominate region with a revenue share of 54.6 % in 2024 and is projected to grow at a CAGR of 30.2 % from 2025 to 2030, achieving USD 74.17 billion at the end of the forecast period (Grand View Research, 2024). Finally, the traction battery is the EVs energy storage system—responsible for a significant portion of the initial vehicle cost (Palmer et al., 2018), vehicle performance, range, and safety—and valued with a market size of USD 73.65 billion in 2024, which is expanding to USD 495.50 billion by 2034 with a CAGR of 21 % in the forecasting period 2024 to 2034. (Precedence Research, 2024)” [34]

“Regulation as key for market transformation: Regulatory roadmaps are crucial levels for the development of the EV market, as they provide political and legal signals for the steering of upcoming investments, innovation, and strategic decisions in corporations by reducing uncertainty for the automotive industry. In the EU the following roadmaps and acts are in force, steering the entire industry into the desired pathways:

- a) **2Zero Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda** (EGVIAfor2Zero, 2024)

- b) **Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy** (EC, 2020)
- c) **European Green Deal** (EC, 2019)
- d) **Fit for 55 Package** (EC, 2021)
- e) **ERTRAC Mapping of Technology Options for Sustainable Energies and Powertrains for Road Transport** (ERTRAC, 2022)
- f) **European Data Strategy** (EC, 2025a)
- g) **EU Artificial Intelligence Act** (European Parliament, 2025)
- h) **EU Cybersecurity Strategy** (EC, 2025b)” [34]

“Changing user needs: The roadmaps, regulations, and acts listed are driving the transformation of the global automotive industry as confirmed by the outlined market situation and well in-line with the ongoing trends on electrification, digitalization, CCAM, regulations, sustainability, and new business models. A McKinsey article reveals that (a) customers are increasingly interested in sustainable modes of transport like multimodal transport, autonomous shuttle services, and Level 4 assistance systems (b) 42 % of the respondents want to have an EV as their next car and 69 % want more connectivity services installed, (c) EV owners want to have features on demand, the option on personal configurations, as well as pre-delivery and post-purchase configurations-change options (Heineke et al., 2024). According to an IBM Institute for Business Value article based on the feedback of more than 1,200 automotive executives, by 2035 (a) vehicles will be software-defined and AI-powered (75 % of the respondents agreed on that), (b) R&D expenditures on software-defined products will increase to 58 % (almost tripling the number), (c) 51 % of the revenue is coming from digital- and software-related sources like connectivity, vehicle subscription or autonomous driving capabilities (Suzuki et al., 2024), enabling data monetization and therefore the establishment of new business models.” [34]

“Regional specificities: A recent study from Roland Berger (2024) identified four mega trends setting the rules in the automotive industry, namely Polarization (considering geopolitical friction, various national or regional regulation, changing customer habits, and macro-economic shifts), Automation, Connectivity, and Electrification. The PwC (2025) publication is expecting impacts on OEMs by uncertain tariffs and emission regulations, inconsistent sustainability measures, uncertain market reaction on EVs and advanced technologies, software-defined vehicles (SDVs), and increased competition especially from China. A Deloitte study indicates that (a) the preferred vehicle propulsion technology strongly varies among different markets, (b) customers are increasingly willing to switch the OEM for their next vehicle, (c) utilization of AI for advancements in autonomous driving is expected to be beneficial, and (d) especially younger customers are willing to prioritize mobility-as-a-service solutions over vehicle ownership (Walker & Proff, 2025). The multifaceted changes impact the whole value chain of a vehicle, enabling new players an easier market entry and the upheaval of new business models focusing on servitization, sharing formats, and circularity by which OEMs seek to monetize software, data, and energy-efficiency advantages (Nieuwenhuis, 2018).” [34]

7 Conclusion

In the deliverable highlighter on exemplary communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities and an overview on the conducted activities are provided. In-depth assessments of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities are not part of this deliverable D7.3 but will be included in EM-TECH's final reporting.

The included sustainability concepts addresses (1) the nine jointly generated one pagers on EM-TECH's project outcomes to increase EM-TECH's visibility and the selling of the project partners' achievements, (2) the analyses of EM-TECH's macro-environment, and (3) the market situation, roadmaps, and trends of the automotive ecosystem to gain a better understanding and a sharpened sensitivity for the ongoing transitions. With these activities the EM-TECH project partners are well-prepared to maximize the impact of EM-TECH's project outcomes beyond the termination of the project.

7.1 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

The survey duration has been extended to receive all project partner's exploitation pathways, also leading to the slight delay of submission of the document.

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9 Appendix

In the following subsections of the appendix, the VPCs and BMCs drafted by AIG and consolidated by the respective EM-TECH project partner can be found.

9.1 AVL's VPC and BMC

Figure 12: AVL's VPC

Figure 13: AVL's BMC

9.2 TUIL's VPC and BMC

Figure 14: TUIL's VPC

Figure 15: TUIL's BMC

9.3 POLITO's VPC and BMC

Figure 16: POLITO'S VPC

Figure 17: POLITO's BMC

9.4 ELA's VPC and BMC

Figure 18: ELA's VPC

Figure 19: ELA's BMC

9.5 I&M's VPC and BMC

Figure 20: I&M's VPC

Figure 21: I&M's BMC

9.6 URBANGOLD's VPC and BMC

Figure 22: URBANGOLD's VPC

Figure 23: URBANGOLD's BMC

9.7 AIG's VPC and BMC

Figure 24: AIG's VPC

Figure 25: AIG's BMC

9.8 USR's VPC and BMC

Figure 26: USR's VPC

Figure 27: USR's BMC

9.9 UBATH's VPC and BMC

Figure 28: UBATH's VPC

Figure 29: UBATH's BMC

9.10 TRX's VPC and BMC

Figure 30: TRX's VPC

Figure 31: TRX's BMC